
Predicción del abandono en la plataforma de educación digital ProFuturo utilizando técnicas de Machine Learning y análisis de datos

Dropout Prediction in ProFuturo Educational Platform using Machine Learning and Data Analysis Techniques

Alejandro Prieto Ramírez 1*, aprietora@upsa.es 1 Facultad de Informática, Universidad Pontificia de Salamanca, 2 ProFuturo, Fundación Telefónica.

*Autor de correspondencia: aprietora@upsa.es

ABSTRACT.

Predicting dropout rates accurately on digital education platforms such as ProFuturo will enable preventive measures to be taken, significantly reducing dropout rates and optimizing the use of resources. Several authors have addressed this problem using machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques with encouraging results. However, most of the approaches are based only on demographic variables or the course completion certificate discarding relevant information available in Moodle platform. Furthermore, they obtain moderate success rates and are not easily interpretable in terms of the indicators considered.

In this paper we propose a novel methodology for accurate dropout prediction that takes into account all informative variables from Moodle. The approach is based on simple machine learning models and maintains high interpretability in terms of input variables. The experimental results show that a methodology based on Random Forest can achieve high detection probability (91%) without compromising specificity with a value of 88%. Moreover, the application of SHAP algorithm has provided high interpretability to understand the role of different variables.

Keywords

Dropout, Machine learning, Random Forest, Logistic Regression LI

1. Introduction

ProFuturo is a non-profit foundation that provides quality digital education to disadvantaged countries around the world. To this aim, ProFuturo has designed digital courses offered through the Moodle platform, both for teachers and for students. Teacher training through these courses plays a key role in providing quality education to students. However, teachers often drop out of the course in the first few days which represents a significant loss of resources and reduces quality of teaching. ProFuturo's experience shows that launching preventive measures such as reminder emails can help reduce the dropout rates significantly. Moreover, understanding the factors that are significantly associated to the drop-out will enable better investment planning. Due to the high number of students, schools and the complexity of the data, artificial intelligence and data analysis techniques are

expected to contribute significantly to solving this problem.

Several authors have applied Artificial Intelligence models to predict dropout with encouraging results. Thus, the Tampere University [1] have considered the data obtained from Moodle platform to predict the dropout rates based on student's graduation. Although it achieves good error rates, predictions are only based on demographic and financial data missing relevant information available in ProFuturo education platform. Moreover, the paper focuses solely on prediction and does not study the associations between the measured indicators and dropout.

Another paper by a group of Necmettin Erbakan University [2] focuses on predicting the dropout in each course. Despite more educational variables are included, the prediction accuracy is limited to 75% and the complexity of the machine learning algorithms considered is significantly greater. Moreover, the

association between the input variables and the dropout is not studied.

Finally, other research published by Studies in Higher Education [3] uses linear and nonlinear models to improve the efficiency of their predictive models. However, they only consider sociological and demographic features at the beginning of the course. In addition, they lose information about the student's progress over time.

In this paper we propose a novel methodology based on the variables of the Moodle platform collected by ProFuturo and non-linear machine learning techniques to predict the dropout accurately. Input variables include student information such as last access to the platform, course duration, or course type. Besides, an explainable methodology based on SHAP has been implemented that allow us to interpret the results in terms of relevant indicators for students. The experimental results show that a non-linear machine learning algorithm such as Random Forest can predict the dropout with high accuracy improving significantly other linear methods and keeping high computational efficiency. Besides, the SHAP algorithm helps to understand the role of some input variables in student dropout.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the dataset considered and the methods employed. Section 3 presents the experimental results.

2. Materiales and Methods

2.1. Dataset Description

The dataset is retrieved from ProFuturo educational database for teachers that is generated automatically from courses offered under Moodle platform. The number of teachers, schools and countries participating in the study is shown in table 1.

Tabla 1. Data distribution

Feature	Quantity
Teachers	180270
Schools	23406
Countries	72

The structure of the database and the relationship between different tables is shown in figure 1.

Figura 1. Data base structure

Users: Where the information related to the user is located. (sample size: 5692953)

Course: Keeps the course related data. (sample size: 3334)

Module: Has the information for each course the certain assignments that compose it. (sample size: 32363)

Course_completion: Relates the users enrolled in a course. (sample size: 5711672)

Module_course_completion: Saves the state of the modules assigned to each user in each course. (sample size: 5692539)

Category: Different classifications of the courses. (sample size: 731)

The database includes 163 features, but most important ones for dropout prediction are described next.

- **Completion_state:** Determines whether the user has completed a module. (1 completed, 0 not completed)
- **Module_name:** The name of the assignment known in Moodle platforms as modules. (“2.3. Análisis de un caso”)
- **Course_duration:** The period of time the platform managers assume a course might take to complete. Expressed by the number of days.
- **Completion_viewed:** Whether the student has or has not viewed the module or assignment. (1 viewed, 0 not viewed)
- **Category_name:** A general category under which the course is defined.(“expaula_es_general”)
- **Catnivel_3,4:** Subcategories to specify the nature of the course. Level 3 categories define

schools of knowledge (“Escuela de Competencia Digital”) Level 4 determines the theme (“Docentes Digitales: Videos interactivos”)

- **Course_name:** The name of the course. (“[VO] Level Up: Learning together... Let's practice! (Mentored)”)
- **Department:** The assigned team to manage the user expedient (“CO_S309868”)
- **Certificate_name:** The name of a certificate if exist. (“Certificado ";JUMP Math! Matemáticas al alcanc...”, “Unknown”)
- **School_name:** The name of the school mentoring. (“Otra escuela México_FD”)
- **Lastaccess:** When the student last access the learning platform. Express as a date time instance.
- **Firstaccess:** Date when user access the platform for the first time.
- **Dateofbirth:** The registered date of birth.
- **City:** Where the user lives.(“Canto del Llano, Santiago”)
- **Username:** The name of the user.
- **Course_timemodified_completion:** Time and date where the course information was updated for the last time.
- **Startdate:** Moment of time where the course is supposed to start.
- **Enddate:** Moment of time where the course is supposed to end.
- **Completion_timeenrrolled:** Instance of time where the student enrrolls in a course.
- **Completion_timestarted:** Date when the student first interacts with a course.

2.2. Workflow

We have developed a methodology to handle this complex dataset that includes all the steps, from the ingestion and pre-processing of the database to the dropout prediction, feature selection and interpretability. The pipeline of the methodology is shown in figure 2.

The main blocks are described next:

- Step 1: Cleaning and data preprocessing
- Step 2: Removing inconsistencies in input/output variables.
- Step 3: The information is re-organized considering the course as unity instead the module.

Figura 2. Workflow diagram

2.2.1. Step 1: Cleaning and data preprocessing

Once the database is ingested, several methods are applied to clean and improve data quality. Thus, only obligatory courses are selected and meaningless registers with missing target variable or missing values in a large number of indicators are filtered out.

Consistency between tables is checked and a single table is generated. Regarding the variables, several feature selection methods have been applied to remove highly correlated variables with the target as well as redundant features. For categorical variables the chi-square correlation measure is considered to evaluate the association with the target [4]. The mutual information based on Shannon entropy is used to evaluate the correlation among variables and to remove redundant features [5]. The 25th percentile has been set as the threshold for filtering characteristics. Finally, to avoid the problem of data imbalance, a strategy of undersampling has been applied. This does not result in any loss of information because of the large number of records available.

2.2.2. Step 2: Removing inconsistencies in input/output variables

Several input variables correspond to dates that are either inconsistent or have not been entered. Missing dates are imputed using k-nearest neighbor algorithm [6].

Similarly, inconsistent dates are also imputed using k-NN or removed if they exceed 20% of the sample size. The dates have been converted to periods of time and transformed using trigonometric functions where necessary.

The second type of inconsistency occurs in the output variable and can have a very negative effect on

the predictor training. Thus, some students have not completed the course simply because they did not have time to finish it when the data was collected. Two tests have been implemented to avoid this problem. The first method analyzes the probability distribution of the time spent by students who have completed the course, removes outliers, and estimates a maximum time threshold for completing the course. Students who have been taking a course for less than the threshold still have time to finish it. The second test compares the last access time with the probability distribution for students that have completed the course. Students who verify both tests still have time to finish and are removed.

2.2.3. Step 3: Definition of the set of input variables

Moodle courses can incorporate several modules. Some variables are inherited directly from the modules, while others are defined in the courses, taking into account a set of module variables. After that, feature selection is applied to remove noisy variables. This step will allow to improve the computational efficiency in the training phase, will help to reduce the overfitting and will enhance the interpretability of the models.

We have compared different linear and non-linear feature selection methods. The first two methods are based on non-linear correlation measures independent of the classifier. Thus, the chi-square measure allow us to evaluate non-linear correlations among categorical variables [7], [8]. For the dataset at hand most variables are categorical and continuous variables are discretized using bins. Features are considered significant with a p-value smaller than 0.05 [9].

An alternative measure considered by other authors is the Mutual Information (MI) [10]. In this paper we have considered MI based on Shannon entropy and continuous variables have been discretized using bins. Finally, we have implemented a wrapper methods using the Mean Decrease Impurity strategy based on Random Forest that selects features based on the non-linear association with the target [11]. Finally, we have implemented a widely used method such as Lasso logistic regression that shrinks the coefficient of non-relevant variables to zero [12], [13].

2.3. Predictive Models

Once the data has been preprocessed and the variables selected, two machine learning algorithms are applied to predict the dropout. The first one is based on the logistic regression using a lasso penalty. The lasso penalty allows to achieve a balance between minimum number of variables and accuracy. This kind of models are linear, robust to overfitting and easily interpretable in terms of input variables. They have been successfully applied by other authors [13]. However, for strongly nonlinear problems, these types of models exhibit high bias, which degrades their performance. Therefore, we have considered also a non-linear model such as Random Forest [14]. This model is very robust against overfitting although it is more difficult to interpret it in terms of the input variables. To overcome this drawback, we have applied SHAP algorithm which will enable us to understand which factors are most decisive in causing students dropout [15].

3. Results and discussions

Random Forest improves significantly the probability of dropout detection (14%) while reducing the probability of false positives (17%). This suggests that Random Forest is able to better modeling the nonlinear nature of the data while keeping the robustness against overfitting.

Table 2. LR modules report

Class	Precision	Recall
Dropout	0.69	0.72
Graduate	0.72	0.69
Accuracy	0.70	

Table 3. RF modules report

Class	Precision	Recall
Dropout	0.86	0.86
Graduate	0.87	0.86
Accuracy	0.86	

Most researchers that predict the dropout in Moodle work with courses, Thus, for the sake of comparison, we

have applied the two previous models to the prediction of dropout in courses instead of modules.

Tabla 4. LR courses report

Class	Precision	Recall
Dropout	0.67	0.64
Graduate	0.66	0.68
Accuracy	0.66	

Tabla 5. RF courses report

Class	Precision	Recall
Dropout	0.74	0.81
Graduate	0.79	0.72
Accuracy	0.76	

As we have mentioned earlier feature selection helps to avoid the overfitting improving the model performance and the computational efficiency. In the next experiment, the optimal subset of features is obtained by Mean Decrease Impurity based on Random Forest (see section 2.2.3). figure 3 shows that the accuracy is maximized considering only 40% of informative features and with only 30% it is slightly worse.

Figure 3. Cross-validation accuracy for different number of features

Therefore, we have considered the subset with only 30% of informative features for all the models tested. To get a deeper insight into this problem all the input variables are ranked using the Random Forest feature importance index. figure 4 visualizes the variables ranked in descending order according to the relevance index. To select the informative variables, we have generated a random variable removing all features with smaller relevance index. figure 4 shows that some variables such as course duration or last access are strongly associated to the dropout as expected.

Figure 4. RF feature importance

The final model is able to identify correctly the 91% of dropout cases without compromising specificity with a value of 0.88. The model is based on a small number of features which improves the interpretability and reduces the time spent in training phase.

Tabla 6. RF 30% modules report

Class	Precision	Recall
Dropout	0.88	0.91
Graduate	0.92	0.88
Accuracy	0.90	

Although Random Forest achieves excellent results, it is not easily interpretable in terms of the input variables. To avoid this problem, we have considered SHAP algorithm. Figure 5 shows a Beeswarm plot for the SHAP values. We can see that most relevant variables are related to the type of course, duration and school name. The name of the course varies greatly, and only in some mathematics-related courses does it significantly increase dropout rates. Similarly, long courses can increase dropout rates, although not always, while short courses have no influence on dropout rates.

Figura 5. SHAP diagram

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we have proposed a methodology for predicting dropout rates on the ProFuturo digital education platform. We have compared the performance of a linear and non-linear predictor considering Mean Decrease Impurity based on Random Forest. Finally, we have applied an explainable AI technique to interpret the model.

The experimental results show that our methodology is able to predict the dropout rates with high accuracy based on a small subset of significant features. The

probability of detecting dropout is high and the application of SHAP algorithm provides the school administrators with relevant information in order to take corrective actions.

Future research lines will focus on the application of more complex models based on deep learning neural networks.

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CONFLICTO DE INTERESES

- Los autores declaran no tener algún conflicto de interés.

CONTRIBUCIÓN Y APROBACIÓN DE LOS AUTORES

Alejandro Prieto Ramírez: Investigación, Redacción, Manuel Martín-Merino Acera: Supervisión, Redacción - Revisión y edición, Oscar Pérez Del Oso: Supervisión, Conceptualización, Manuel J Ruiz García: Supervisión, Conceptualización, Carmen Rodríguez Hernández: supervisión, Conceptualización.

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